

RABEK
Regionalna asocijacija za bezbednost i krizni menadžment

**GLOBAL
SECURITY**

7th INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC - PROFESSIONAL CONFERENCE

SECURITY AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT -THEORY AND PRACTICE

SAFETY FOR THE FUTURE 2021

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BELGRADE 2021

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Design

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Edition

30 copies

The press:

Štamparija Donat Graf, Grocka, Belgrade

ISBN

978-86-80692-08-1

Note:

The authors opinions expressed in this book do not necessary reflect the views of the institution in which they are employed

THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND MENTAL HEALTH OF ELECTRICAL FITTERS (INCREASED RISK JOB)

Danica Vukajlović¹, PhD Marija Jevtić², PhD Mirjana Laban³

¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 6, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, vukajlovicdanica@yahoo.com

² University of Novi Sad, Medical Faculty, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, marija.jevtic@uns.ac.rs

³ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 6, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, mlaban@uns.ac.rs

Abstract: *The COVID-19 virus pandemic is a global crisis, with consequences reflected on the mental health of people globally during the pandemic, and that will be recorded in the future. Mental health of employees is important for the work process of every company, since any health disturbance results in reduced productivity and possible errors while performing work tasks. This paper analyses the impact of the current pandemic crisis on the mental health of employees in the electricity supply system, as workers in one of the sectors of critical infrastructure and workers whose jobs involve increased risk. The survey, conducted via a questionnaire, involved 109 workers, with the aim to determine the impact of the pandemic crisis on their mental health, as well as to propose measures that could provide support and assistance to this group of workers in the future, if we should again face similar challenges.*

Key words: *pandemic, electricity supply system, mental health*

1. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 is an infection caused by a new type of corona virus SARS-CoV-2 [1]. Coronaviruses (CoV) are a large family of viruses causing diseases ranging from the common cold to serious illnesses such as: Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS-CoV) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS-CoV) [2]. According to WHO and CDC data, COVID-19 is spread via droplets, most often when people talk, sneeze, cough, etc.

The coronavirus COVID-19 appeared in China, in the city of Wuhan, with the first reported case in early December 2019 [1]. After that, the virus began to spread rapidly through various regions of China, and on December 31, 2019, the WHO office in China was informed about cases of pneumonia with an unknown cause. On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization declared a state of concern, and on March 11, 2020 the World Health Organization declared the COVID-19 pandemic.

Over one year after the announcement of the first case in China, on January 7, 2021 in the world, in 222 countries, 85,929,428 cases of infection had been registered, with 1,860,100 fatal outcomes.

According to data of the Institute of Public Health "Milan Jovanović Batut", the first case of COVID-19 in the Republic of Serbia was recorded on March 6, 2020. From the beginning when the epidemic was proclaimed until January 7, 2021, in the Republic of Serbia 353,907 cases were registered, with 3,479 fatal outcomes [4].

Due to virus characteristics and the request of the World Health Organization not to perform autopsies, it is still unknown what lasting consequences it will have on human health. A special cause for worry is the situation that this virus will not only have consequences for human lives and health, but will also have consequences for mental health.

2. ELECTRICAL FITTERS – A JOB WITH INCREASED RISK

The job of electrical fitter is among high-risk jobs. Some of the definitions that characterize high-risk jobs are listed below [3].

Risk is the probability of injury, illness or damage to the health of an employee due to hazards.

Risk assessment is the systematic recording and assessment of all factors in the work process that can cause injuries at work, illnesses or damage to health and the determination of possibilities, i.e. ways to prevent, eliminate or reduce the risk.

A job with increased risk is a job established by the document on risk assessment where, regardless of fully applied measures in accordance with this Law, there are circumstances that may endanger the safety and health of an employee.

The person in charge of work safety and health is a person performing activities related to safety and health at work, who has passed the professional exam on practical training and who is appointed by the employer to perform these tasks by a written document.

According to the Council of Europe and Great Britain, energy is one of the basic sectors of critical infrastructure, and accordingly it can be safely concluded that electrical fitters are workers within this critical infrastructure, and are among its carriers.

Based on the answers provided in a survey conducted on a group of electrical fitters, this research aims to determine what impact the COVID-19 pandemic has had on the mental state, work conditions and safety of employees working as electrical fitters, to propose measures to improve conditions and work organization, so that employees on those jobs can perform their work tasks more easily without stressful situations that would have a potential negative impact on their mental health.

3. RESEARCH AND RESULTS

109 respondents responded to the survey regarding the impact of the COVID pandemic on the psychological and social well-being of electrical fitters working within critical infrastructure on jobs with increased risk.

Table 1: Respondents' answers - age

Respondents' age	Under 20 0.9%	21 to 30 43.9%	31 to 40 36.4%	41 to 50 17.8%	Over 50 0.9%
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Table 1 contains responses of respondents who answered the survey question about their age, showing that the highest percentage of respondents (43.9%) were aged between 21 and 30 years.

Table 2: Respondents' answers - place of residence

Respondent's place of residence	City 46.2%	Village 53.8%
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Table 2 contains responses of respondents who answered the survey question about their place of residence, showing that a higher percentage of respondents were living in villages (53.8%).

Table 3: Respondents' answers – housing unit.

Respondent's housing unit	Apartment 18.7%	House 81,3%
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Table 3 contains responses of respondents who answered the survey question about their housing unit. Results show that a higher percentage of respondents were living in houses (81.3%).

Table 4: Respondents' answers – marital status

Respondent's marital status	Married 57.5%	Divorced 0.9%	Single 41.5%
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Table 4 contains responses of respondents about their marital status. Results show that the highest percentage of respondents were married (57.5%).

Table 5: Respondents' answers – children

Respondents' children	One child 21.7%	Two children 25.5%	Three children 6.6%	More than three children 0%	No children 47.2%	Underaged children 21.7%	Children under 7 years of age 17.8%
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Table 5 contains responses of respondents about their children. Obtained results show that the highest percentage of respondents had children, and that 21.7% had one child, 25.5% had two children, and 0.6% had three children.

Table 6: Structure of households respondents live in

Single person household 7.5 %
Two member household 21.5 %
Three member household 17.8 %
Household with more than three members 44.9 %
Household with members over 65 years 33.6 %
Household with children under 7 years 32.7 %
Hpuisehold with adult children 7.5 %
Household with pets 19.6 %

Table 6 contains responses of respondents about the structure of their households. Obtained results show that the highest number of respondents lived in households of over three members (44.9%).

Table 7: Respondents' answers – intensity of work engagement

Intensity of work engagement during the pandemic	Increased 18.7%	Unchanged 60.7%	Decreased 20.6%
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Table 7 contains responses of respondents about the intensity of their work engagement. Obtained results show that for the highest percentage (60,7%) the intensity of their work engagement remained unchanged.

Table 8: Respondents' answers – years of work experience

Years of work experience	Up to 5 years 34.6%	5 to 15 years 57.9%	15 to 20 years 5.6%	20 to 25 years 0.9%	Over 25 years 0.9%
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Table 8 contains responses of respondents about their years of work experience. Obtained results show that the highest percentage of respondents (57.9%) had 5 to 15 years of work experience.

Table 9: Respondents' answers – effect of the pandemic on their work engagement

Effect of the pandemic on work engagement	No effect 71%	Prevented from performing work tasks 11.2%	Overburdened with work tasks 5.6%	Injured during the pandemic 0.9%	On sick leave during work engagement 10.3%	Noted reduced concentration while performing work tasks 0.9%
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Table 9 contains responses of respondents about the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on their work engagement. Obtained results show that in 71% of cases the COVID-19 pandemic had no effect on work engagement.

Table 10: Respondents' answers – effect of the pandemic on daily life

Effect of the pandemic on daily life	Separation from friends 42.1%	Separation from the family 3.7%	Fear of job loss 16.8%	Loneliness 3.7%	Worry about loved ones 57%	Worry about a pet 2.8%	Anxiety 10.3%	No significant effect 32.7%
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Table 10 contains responses of respondents about effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on their daily life. Obtained results show that the highest number of respondents worried about their loved ones (57%), and that separation from friends had the highest impact on respondents (42.1%).

Table 11: Respondents' answers – effect of measures during the pandemic and special work conditions on their health status

Effect of measures during the pandemic and special work conditions on the respondent	Sleeping problems 5.7%	Weight loss 2.8%	Weight gain and irregular diet 17%	Intensified bad habits 5.7%	Non-smokers who did not start smoking during the pandemic 36.8%	No effect on physical health 66%	Negative effect of the pandemic on the health status 4.7%
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Table 11 contains responses of respondents about the effect of measures during the COVID-19 pandemic on their health status. Obtained results show that at the time of the survey, for the highest percentage (66%) the COVID-19 pandemic had no effect on their health status.

Table 12: Respondents' answers – personal illness during COVID-19

Respondents falling ill with COVID-19	Yes 19.6%	No 80.4%
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Table 12 contains responses of respondents to the question if they personally fell ill with COVID-19 during the pandemic. Obtained results show that the majority of respondents (80.4%) were not ill during the pandemic.

Table 13: Respondents' answers – COVID-19 illness among persons close to the respondents

A close person falling ill with COVID-19	Yes 39.3%	No 60.7%
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Table 13 contains responses of respondents to the question if any persons close to them fell ill with COVID-19. Obtained results show that in most cases (60.7%) no close persons fell ill.

Table 14: Respondents' answers – close persons who died during the COVID-19 pandemic

Close persons who died from COVID-19	Yes 4.7%	No 95.3%
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Table 14 contains results about persons close to the respondents who died from COVID-19. Obtained results show that for the highest percentage (95.3%) there were no deaths.

Table 15: Respondents' answers – own testing during the COVID-19 pandemic

Was the respondent tested for COVID-19 once or more than once since the beginning of the pandemic	Yes 37.4%	No, no test was needed 52.3%	No, but the respondent considered it 9.3%	Number of respondents who requested to be tested but were not 0.9%
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Table 15 contains results about respondents' testing for COVID-19. Obtained results show that the majority of respondents were not tested during the pandemic (52.3%), with the justification that it was not necessary.

Table 16: Respondents' answers – availability of money for basic needs

Did the respondent have enough money for basic needs	Yes 46.7%	No 17.8%	Partially 35.5%
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Table 16 contains responses of respondents about the availability of enough money during the COVID-19 pandemic. Obtained results show that 17.8% did not have enough money, and 35.5% partially had money, which is also the most frequent response to this question.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND MEASURES

Based on results obtained in the survey, it can be seen that respondents were exclusively men with ages mostly varying from 21 to 40 years, therefore belonging to the younger population. According to reports of health organizations to date, COVID-19 mostly affects the elderly population, which was therefore the most endangered during the COVID-19 pandemic. The very reason is that the body of younger is more resistant and hardy than the body of older individuals. Based on these data, at the very beginning of the research, we can present the assumption that our respondents employed as electrical fitters belonged to a population that less endangered by the COVID-19 virus.

By analysing the following two questions, respondent's place of residence and housing unit, we see that numbers of those residing in villages and in cities are almost equal, while a significantly higher number of respondents answered that their housing unit is a house. During the period we spent in quarantine, this provided significant benefits and relief for mental health, due to the fact that a majority of respondents (81%) could stay in the yard, in the open air, be exposed to the Sun, which is a natural source of vitamin D during summer days.

Based on the following questions and answers about whether they are married, whether they have children and how many members make up their household, majority answers show that the respondents who were surveyed did not live alone in their home, and that the possibility of person to person transmission within the household itself was increased, and thus also the potential worry not to infect their household and loved ones.

According to provided answers, the intensity of work engagement of the group of respondents - electrical fitters for 60.7% mostly remained unchanged. On the basis of this, we can conclude that even in times of a global epidemic, workers on these jobs were not spared from work tasks and exposure to the possibilities of falling ill.

The respondents' years of work experience show that the majority of jobs are occupied by respondents with work experience of 5 to 15 years (57.9%), based on which we can conclude that they are experienced fitters who, based on education and acquired experience, can certainly be classified into the group of experienced workers. Also, the majority of respondents (71%) stated that the pandemic did not have an effect on their work engagement, more precisely that they fulfilled their work obligations as regularly as before the pandemic.

Speaking about the daily life of these respondents, the highest percentage of changes was recorded relevant to separation from friends (42.1%), which certainly results in reduced socializing and fear of job loss (16.8%), causing not at all pleasant feelings in people. Also, 17% of respondents gained weight and ate irregularly, while 2.8% noticed weight loss. Both cases can be attributed to consequences of stress, for the reason that consequences of stress are reflected in the sense of excessive or reduced nutrition, depending on the person. 5.7% of respondents had sleep problems, and 4.7% said that the pandemic had a negative impact on their health. A consequence of stress, of the feeling of fear, and lack of socialization in humans, are depressive and anxious states, increased nervousness, feelings of exhaustion, insomnia, and all this can lead to health disorders that become manifest in the near and the distant future.

Speaking specifically about the COVID-19 virus disease, 19.6% of respondents fell ill, while 39.3% had a case of illness of a person close to them, and 4.7% experienced a death in the circle of people they were close with.

Therefore, in addition to the hard work they performed and with all the personal protection measures taken at work, our respondents had cases where they themselves fell ill, which could lead to creating panic and fear in other colleagues who directly or indirectly had contact with them.

In the 37.4% of respondents who underwent PCR testing for COVID-19, fear and panic behavior was confirmed, as illustrated by the fact that the number of persons tested in this group of workers was higher than the number of those who became ill.

Speaking specifically about whether respondents had enough money for their basic needs, 35.5% stated that they had money partially, and 17.8% that they had no money at all. Certainly, the pandemic, and the measures prescribed to preserve personal health, adversely affected the material status of our respondents, although based on the survey we can see that for the most part their work productivity was not reduced.

Based on obtained research results, and conclusions about the impact on the life, work and health of respondents, some of the measures recommended to improve working conditions on electrical fitter jobs in order to reduce possibility of infection, fear, worry and all else that belongs to workers' life and health could be the following:

- Introduction of work in shifts so that fewer workers are in the same place at the same time,
- Introduction of greater control over the application of protective devices (masks, disinfectants, etc.),
- Shorter work hours,
- Forming working groups of two electrical fitters, and communication via means of communication,